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An Honest and Compelling Life Narrative: Ismat Chughtai's *A Life in Words*

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Abstract:

Ismat Chughtai is undoubtedly one of the most fearless as well as controversial women writers of the Indian subcontinent. A prominent 'progressive' and ardent feminist voice in the Urdu literary world, Chughtai boldly wrote against the gendered double standards and oppressive patriarchal structures and denounced the exploitation of the poor, underprivileged and marginalized sections of the society. Her memoir, *Kaghazi Hai Pairahan*, translated into English as *A Life in Words*, is expressive of her honest and bold views on myriad issues ranging from male hegemony, female illiteracy and subjugation to religious bigotry, false morality, oppression of the poor and underprivileged, divisions along caste, creed, religion, factions and wars. Narrating incidents from her personal life and projecting them in a wider social perspective, she strongly criticizes the societal and patriarchal customs and norms and advocates for the rights and freedom of women. This paper attempts to explore Ismat Chughtai's memoir as an honest, bold and compelling life narrative that deals with not only personal but also political and global issues.

Keywords: Progressive, iconoclast, sexuality, memoir, patriarchal, feminist, aristocracy, document, feudal, conservative.

Described as one of the most evocative and powerful voices in Urdu literature, Ismat Chughtai (1911-1991) appeared on the literary horizon when women in South Asia were still sequestered and suppressed. Experimenting in multiple literary genres ranging from the traditional *afsanas*, novels, novellas and dramas to writing and collaborating on several screen plays, Ismat Chughtai made a distinct mark in the literary world with her fiery, outspoken, courageous and controversial style of writing. Her writings, that dealt mainly with themes focusing on exploration of female sexuality, exposure and questioning of false morality, hypocrisy and double standards of the Indian middle class, established Ismat Chughtai as an iconoclast who not only opened new avenues for women writers in Urdu fiction but also redefined the norms of Urdu literature. Rakshanda Jalil rightly observes, "In her hands Urdu acquired a new zest, an added spice that made it not only more readable, but also better equipped to reflect new concerns that had been hitherto considered beyond the pale of literature". (Jalil 324)

Popularly addressed as "the grand dame of Urdu fiction"(Naqvi 37), Ismat Chughtai was a rebel who took to writing when women, particularly of the Indian subcontinent, were bound by strict patriarchal restrictions that did not allow them freedom and hampered their involvement in intellectual pursuits. "She developed the markings of a feminist in the early forties when the concept of feminism was in its nascent stage, even in the West" (Naqvi 37) and spoke her mind without reservations.

Ismat Chughtai's literary oeuvre includes a rich collection of short stories, novels, novellas, plays, several essays and non-fictional writings originally written in Urdu and widely translated into English and several other languages. "Dheet", "Kafir", "Gainda" and "Khidmatgaar" are some of her well-known short stories. She is, however, most famous for her short story titled "Lihaaf" which created a furore upon its publication in 1942 on account of its theme that dealt with lesbianism and sexual abuse. *Kaliyan, Choten, Ek Baat, Chhui Mui,*

Do Haath, Badan ki Khushboo, Amarbel, Thori Si Paagal and *Aadhi Aurat Aadha Khwaab* are her well known collections of short stories. Her novels include *Ziddi* (1941), *Tehri Lakeer* (1943), *Saudai* (1964), *Ajeeb Aadmi* (1970) and *Ek Qatra Khoon* (1975). In addition to novellas - *Masooma* (1961), *Dil ki Duniya* (1966) and *Jungli Kabootar* (1970) , she also wrote several plays including *Fasadi* (1938), *Intikhab* (1939), *Dozakhi* (1960), *Tanhai ka Zaher* (1977) and others. Her prominent non-fictional writings include an essay titled “Bachpan” and an anthology of essays titled *Hum Log* . She also penned “Dozakhi”, an essay about her brother, Azeem Baig Chughtai, and a piece on Saadat Hasan Manto titled “Mera Dost Mera Dushman”. Chughtai has been widely read, translated, adapted and performed.

Isamt Chughtai’s much acclaimed unfinished memoir *Kaghazi Hai Pairahan* roughly covers a period of twenty two crucial years, from 1920 to 1942, in her life. The memoir originally appeared between March 1979 to May 1980 as chapters in the Urdu journal, *Aaj Kal*. It was first published as a single volume in Urdu posthumously in 1994. In the words of the noted author and critic, M. Asaduddin , “despite the fragmentary nature” of Ismat Chughtai’s memoir and “its gaps and inadequacies, one cannot deny the fact that the individual and the social, the personal and the political come together to make it a unique document in the annals of life-writings by women in Urdu literature” (Asaduddin xxv). M.Asaduddin translated *Kaghazi Hai Pairahan* into English under the title *A Life in Words: Memoirs*. This English translation was published by Penguin Book India in 2012. The *Hindustan Times* applauds the translator for his efforts in attempting the first complete English translation of Ismat Chughtai’s memoir in the following words : “Translator M.Asaduddin has... done a remarkable job , catching all the nuances of Chughtai’s luscious prose and extraordinary wit...”(*A Life in Words*, cover page)

In the words of a critic :

Memoirs are experiential perspectives of an individual's life. Unlike autobiography, it is selective, random and tangled... The purpose of writing memoirs can be of sharing, of exorcising, reliving or eternalizing the memorable moments, events and people of one's life. Memoirs of writers are a window to the psyche, milieu and inspirations of the writer as an individual. (Vaishnav 73)

A Life in Words provides a glimpse into several crucial years in Ismat Chughtai's life from her childhood days and experiences of growing up in a large Muslim household at Badaun, a relatively small town in the state of Uttar Pradesh, during the early decades of the twentieth century to the writing of her controversial story "Lihaaf" for which she had to face a trial at Lahore in 1944 on charges of obscenity. The translator, M.Asaduddin, describes the memoir as "a curious piece of work" which is "not a straightforward autobiography" and is not arranged chronologically. It is rather a fragmented life narrative "written in fits and starts when spurts of memory propelled her to record her reminiscences, without consideration for chronology, repetition or narrative coherence." (Asaduddin x)

The blurb on the book mentions that "Chughtai is searingly honest about her fight to get an education and the struggle to find her own voice as a writer". The narration is not linear and the book, as pointed out by Adheesa Sarkar, appears to be "a collection of jumbled notes, thoughts, memories, anecdotes – woven into the narrative in the same way as they would perhaps occur in a conversation. The reader feels as though Chughtai is talking, chatting continuously...". (Sarkar, *The Telegraph Online*)

Ismat Chughtai was born on 21 August 1911 at Badaun, in Uttar Pradesh. Her father, Mirza Qaseem Baig Chughtai, was a civil servant and mother, Nusrat Khanam, was a homemaker. Her childhood was spent in Agra, Jodhpur, Aligarh and several other cities where her father was posted. Ismat Chughtai belonged to the class of landed aristocracy which, despite its

acceptance of Western liberal education, was still largely conservative and bound with traditions as far as women's role in society was concerned. Her familial world was abound with several submissive, passively suffering, servile women whom she had seen from close quarters. She felt a strong desire to free herself from the narrow confines of this world and carve an identity free from the dictates of the traditional society. Quite early in life, she realized that education was the gateway to the emancipation of women and she made up her mind to achieve it against all odds. She fiercely fought against several obstacles, including the patriarchal notion that education was 'dangerous' for females, to secure a formal education for herself. In so doing, she was able to fulfil an ambition that was still a distant dream for countless other females of her age, particularly those belonging to conservative Muslim households.

Ismat Chughtai's memoir is "a significant document that brings out the angst, anxieties and vulnerabilities of a sensitive woman at a critical juncture in national history, representing Indian women's conflicts with tradition and their desire to be modern" (Deo 216). It is "a work that encapsulates the contemporary female world with a feminist and humanist approach, ruthless honesty, bold individuality and often tongue in cheek satire and humour" (Vaishnav 74). She observes, "A lack of equality is found not only among the rich and the poor; it exists in a more intense form in the power relationship between men and women". (Chughtai 8)

The domestic world Ismat Chughtai inhabited was full of passive, submissive, repressed women who instilled in her a strong sense of dislike and dissatisfaction with conventional womanhood. It is with reference to a number of such women including her mother, sisters, cousins, nieces, aunts, midwives, friends etc that Ismat Chughtai's worldview is shaped and gets reflected in her memoir as she attempts to map, understand and narrate her 'self'. In her memory her mother's image is etched as that of a woman trapped in domesticity and child bearing whose entire world revolved around her familial responsibilities as a wife and mother

to her ten children- six sons and four daughters. She laments the fate of her mother and also of countless other women doomed to a life of patriarchal servility and subjugation. She feels that motherhood for such women was more of a punishment. Remembering her mother, Ismat Chughtai writes:

We were so many siblings that my mother felt nauseated by the very sight of us. One after another we had tumbled to the earth, pummelling and battering her womb. Suffering endlessly from vomiting and labour pains, she looked upon us as objects of her punishment. She had become a grandmother at the age of thirty-five and suffered continual punishment. (Chughtai 1-2)

While Ismat Chughtai portrays her mother with a lot of affection, she also points out the manipulations, deceptions, feminine wiles and covert strategies she often resorted to in order to exercise power, seek happiness and assert herself in familial politics. Ismat Chughtai could not perceive her mother as a role model and she felt withdrawn and alienated from her pattern of womanhood.

With her elder sisters married and busy in their domestic lives, Ismat's childhood and formative years were spent mainly in the midst of her brothers which impacted her personality and viewpoints to a great extent. She would subconsciously try to imitate them in manners and behaviour and even excel them out of sibling rivalry. This developed in her an assertiveness and confidence which otherwise was not encouraged in the females belonging to traditional conservative Muslim families. As an adolescent, with no taste for any make-up, gaudy clothes or desire for decking up, Ismat was very different and somewhat 'unfeminine'.

Her mother, however, disapproved of her ways of living. She was anxious for the future of her daughter who was so different and defiant and whose pursuits were not befitting a woman. She instructed her to develop 'feminine' traits in her. As Ismat Chughtai matured, she

could understand the cause of her mother's anxiety and admits, "Later I found out why my mother was so anxious. This was a man's world, she said, made and distorted by man. A woman is a tiny part of this world and man has made her the object of own love and hatred. Depending on his whims, he worships her or rejects her" (Chughtai 9).

Ismat Chughtai's assertiveness, interests in intellectual pursuits and lack of physical charms were viewed as impediments in the way of her marriage which was the ultimate destiny for a female in the traditional patriarchal society. She often indulged in self-doubts and felt envious of her attractive cousins who, with their expertise in household chores and 'accomplishments' such as knitting, cooking and embroidery, were much appreciated as ideal homemakers.

Recalling her life in Agra, where her family had shifted to after the retirement of her father, Ismat Chughtai writes about the restrictive environment of the city and the hapless, pathetic state of the womenfolk of her neighbourhood. She felt appalled at the helplessness, depression and emaciated condition of the majority of these women subjected to numerous atrocities and exploitative practices in the name of patriarchy. Such women, however, survived on the strength of their superstitious beliefs, on the power of amulets and charms that made them endure their sufferings. The sight of such women induced in Ismat Chughtai a feeling of repulsion at being a woman and she felt angry towards God for the injustice done to her in making her a female, and secretly prayed to God to somehow turn her into a boy.

Quite early in life, Ismat Chughtai felt drawn towards reading and found in books her 'true' friends. She reminisces:

Books have affected me more than anything else in my life. Every book I have read has given me something. I have looked for answers to most of my problems in books and found them. Books have proved to be my closest friends, providing me succour in

moments of sorrow. I have coped with my hours of darkness and a thousand deprivations with the help of these friends. (13-14)

She was an avid reader who enjoyed reading Thomas Hardy, the Bronte sisters, G.B. Shaw and several others. However, the Russian writers, particularly Anton Chekhov, influenced her the most. In Rasheed Jahan, a prominent communist, feminist activist and woman writer of Urdu Literature, Ismat Chughtai found not only a role model but also a literary and political mentor who inspired her with 'progressive' literary ideas. In Ismat Chughtai's words, "Rasheed Jahan left a deep impact on me when I was quite young. I tried to learn candidness and self-respect from her". (Chughtai 11)

She felt a peculiar pleasure in writing which not only proved to be a source of satisfaction and fulfilment but also served as a cathartic exercise that helped her overcome several disappointments, dejections and difficult moments in her life. Writing gave a feeling of authority and 'power' to Ismat Chughtai. Holding a pen and writing on a piece of paper was akin to being with a friend or confidant. She admits, "The pen is my provider as well as my friend and confidant, a friend who keeps me company in my hours of loneliness. While it was with me I have never felt alone" (Chughtai 17). She perceives writing as a 'liberating' exercise that provided her a sense of freedom and power. Through her writing, she could control others, make them laugh or cry or even make them "dance like puppets" before her which gave her a feeling of possessing "the power of the Creator." (Chughtai 17)

Ismat Chughtai was very critical of the feudal society she herself was part of and disapproved of the ways it divided humanity into two classes - the class of the so-called 'haves' or 'masters' and the 'have nots' or 'servants' and the way it licenced the master/feudal class to subject the servant class to utter exploitation, humiliation and subjugation. She felt disturbed and unhappy

with the ways servants were often treated in her own household. Recalling her childhood memories, Ismat Chughtai writes:

As a child I have seen servants treated with such contempt that I developed an intense hatred for the system that allows some to be masters and others to be servants... It left a deep impression on my mind. But as I came in contact with the wider world I realized that the distinctions between the high and the low and between castes are only a sham. The real distinction is between wealth and poverty. This is the way of the world. A rich person, however devout and patriotic, treats the poor like a servant. (Chughtai 2)

Rising above the personal and private, Ismat Chughtai, in her memoir, also voices her concerns for larger, global issues afflicting mankind. She strongly condemns all wars and the selfish motives of the 'few' behind such wars. She views all wars as crimes against humanity. Ismat Chughtai strongly condemns the atrocities perpetrated on human beings across the globe as a result of wars fought between different nations. Referring to the prolonged war in Vietnam and its accompanying bloodbath, she questions in desperation, "Where are the people who can stop it? How long will humanity remain a helpless witness to such spectacles?" (Chughtai 4). She puts forth her opinion in this regard in the following words, "Human beings have ostensibly given up cannibalism, but the truth is that they continue to devour human flesh in some form or the other. I couldn't care less for such a world, and detest the principles of the system which allows this". (Chughtai 4)

Ismat Chughtai also bitterly criticizes the politics of hate and violence and all kinds of divisions on the basis of caste, creed, class, culture or religion. She advocates equality and emerges as a champion of the rights of the underprivileged, deprived sections of the society. She was acutely conscious of the plight of women in a conservative patriarchal society and wrote boldly and

fiercely about it. She “broke the silence and became the harbinger of significant changes in society and literary attitudes and judgements”. (Hasan 104)

Her writing is a testament to the fact that Ismat Chughtai was a ‘progressive’ in the true sense of the word. Her memoir serves as an important document that offers a glimpse into the lives of the contemporary women straddling between the demands of a conservative, traditional, patriarchal world and their own desire for autonomy, identity and selfhood. It is a unique piece of bold, honest and compelling life narrative that offers Ismat Chughtai’s views on personal, political and global issues without any bitterness or negativity. In the words of Adheesa Sarkar:

Throughout her memoir, Chughtai has playfully strewn vital clues to the workings of her mind. They can be found in the unlikeliest of places, suddenly in the middle of a nostalgic recounting, among tense conversations or idle descriptions...Chughtai is never bitter. She defies, but does not accuse. Her discontent is always tempered by mischief and fun, by calm conviction and a warm love of life. (Sarkar, *The Telegraph Online*)

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